

BACTERIAL LIPASE: SOURCES, PRODUCTION & APPLICATION

¹Dipti Chandrakar, ²Priyambda Singh

¹PGStudent, Department of Microbiology, Kalinga University, Chhattisgarh, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Kalinga University, Chhattisgarh, India

Abstract

Being extremely adaptable enzymes, lipases have drawn interest from a variety of industrial processes. Microbial sources can all produce lipase. By 2023, the market for microbial lipase applications is expected to have grown at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.8% from its 2018 estimate of USD 425.0 million to USD 590.2 million. To hydrolyse long chain triglycerides, microbial lipases (EC 3.1.1.3) are required. Because lipase enzymes are derived from microorganisms, they are conceptually active and effective, and they may be used in a wide variety of industrial processes to produce modified molecules. In the developing world, microbial biodegradation of oil pollutants and their derivatives has emerged as the most environmentally beneficial technique. The purpose of this study was to assess the capacity of lipase generated by native bacteria from oil-contaminated soil to biodegrade oil. The isolates of indigenous bacteria were identified as species of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Their ability to produce lipase was demonstrated in their zone of clearance on tween 80 agar plates, and spectrophotometric analyses were used to further confirm the presence of lipase produced by the two bacteria.

Key words- Microbial lipases, oil contaminated, soil isolation, industrial application, transesterification, hydrolysis, sustainable processes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lipases are a class of enzymes that facilitate the hydrolysis of mono, di and triglycerides into free fatty acids and glycerol.[1] Lipases (triacylglycerol acylhydrolases, EC 3.1.1.3) can hydrolyze ester bond of long chain fatty acid which is mainly component of oil. The sources of lipase enzyme are generally found in nature such as plants, animals, yeast, fungi and bacteria[2] for example, *Lactobacillus spp.* [3] *Bacillus stearothermophilus L1* [4]. Bacterial lipases are important enzymes applications in various industries, because of friendly for environment, non-toxic and no harmful residues [5]. For instant, there are widely uses in dairy industry and pharmaceutical industry [6], detergent and surfactant [5], taste or flavor industry [7], agricultural industry, chemical, cosmetic and perfume [5]. Especially, they are applied for biodiesel productions such as lipase enzyme from *Acinetobacter venetianus RAG-1* could produce biodiesel using transesterification process [8]. Lipase production by various bacterial species has been extensively studied and reported. They are found in diverse habitats, including oil processing industries, organic wastes, dairy industries, slaughter-house, decaying foods, oil-contaminated sites, etc [9]. Among different bacteria, *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Bacillus sp.* constitute a major source of lipase enzyme, and members of these bacteria are of interest in biotechnology [10]. Lipases are produced by many microorganisms and higher eukaryotes. Most commercially useful lipases are of microbial origin. Lipase-producing microorganisms have been found in diverse habitats such as industrial wastes, vegetable oil processing factories, dairies, soil contaminated with oil, oilseeds, and decaying food, compost

heaps, coal tips, and hot springs [11]. Microbial lipases have gained special industrial attention due to their stability, selectivity, and broad substrate specificity [12] [13]. Microbial enzymes are also more stable than their corresponding plant and animal enzymes and their production is more convenient and safer [14]. Many microorganisms are known as potential producers of extracellular lipases, including bacteria, yeast, and fungi [15]. A variety of extracellular lipases of bacterial origin with different properties and specificities have been described and characterized. Extracellular lipase was isolated from many different bacterial species, including *Bacillus* [16] and *Pseudomonas* [17] [18]. Particular attention is focused on specific classes of enzymes of species *Pseudomonas*, that are among the first studied and used in biotechnological production but also because of their involvement in bacterial pathogenesis. Lipases are found in a number of *Pseudomonas* [19][20][18]. The bacterial genus *Pseudomonas* secretes a number of extracellular enzymes, which include lipases, in response to fluctuating external nutrients. Interest in *Pseudomonas* lipases stems either from their potential usefulness in a variety of biotechnological applications or from their detrimental effect on stored food products such as refrigerated milk. The majority of the strains of *Pseudomonas* sp. are producers of lipase and phospholipase-C [21]. A simple and reliable method for detecting lipase activity in microorganisms has been described [22]. This method uses the surfactant Tween 80 in a solid medium to identify a lipolytic activity. The formation of opaque zones around the colonies is an indication of lipase production by the organisms. Modifications of this assay use various surfactants in combination with Nile blue or neet's foot oil and Cu^{2+} salts. Also, screening of lipase producers on agar plates is frequently done by using tributyrin as a substrate [23] and clear zones around the colonies indicate production of lipase. Screening systems making use of chromogenic substrates have also been described [24]. Plates of a modified Rhodamine B agar was used to screen lipase activity in a large number of microorganisms. Other versions of this method have been reported [25]. Microbial lipases are mostly extracellular and their production is greatly influenced by medium composition besides physicochemical factors such as temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen. The major factor for the expression of lipase activity has always been reported as the carbon source, since lipases are inducible enzymes. These enzymes are generally produced in the presence of a lipid such as oil or any other inducer, such as triacylglycerols, fatty acids, hydrolysable esters, Tweens, bile salts, and glycerol [26] [27]. However, nitrogen sources and essential micronutrients should also be carefully considered for growth and production optimization. Generally, high productivity has been achieved by culture medium optimization. Optimization of the concentration of each compound that constitutes a cultivation medium is usually a time-consuming procedure. Microbial lipases are produced mostly by submerged culture but solid state fermentation methods can be used also. The use of by-products as substrates for lipase production, adds high value and low-cost substrates may reduce the final cost of the enzyme [28]. As consumer demand for enzyme-modified cheese (EMC) and enzyme-modified dairy ingredients (EMDI) rises along with awareness of animal welfare and produce quality, the lipase market has been greatly expanded [29]. The powdered microbial lipases are anticipated to dominate the microbial lipase markets because they are stable, manageable, and easier to package and transport [30]. At a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.5%, the lipase market is projected to reach \$590.5 million globally by 2020. In 2014, the largest market for lipase consumption was Asia-Pacific [31].

2 Historical background

Enzymes are proteins that can catalyse a variety of chemical and biological reactions both inside and outside of cells. They function at high conversion rates under negligible environmental factors like temperature, pressure, and pH and are extremely specific natural catalysts to different kinds of substrates [32]. In 1856, Claude Bernard identified lipase as an enzyme in pancreatic juice that hydrolysed insoluble oil droplets to produce soluble ones [33]. Following that, lipase production was noted in 1901 in the bacteria *Bacillus prodigiosus*, *B. pyocyaneus*, and *B. fluorescens*. In the present situation, lipase production on a large scale has been detected in the bacteria *Serratia marcescens*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* [34]. In 1994, produced lipolase, the first commercial recombinant lipase, which was then expressed in *Aspergillus oryzae* [35]. Lipase has historically been extracted from the animal pancreas and used as a digestive supplement in either crude or purified form. Numerous new chemical compounds have been synthesised using it in biocatalytic processes [36][37].

2.1 Definition of lipases

Lipases (EC 3.1.1.3), also referred to as triacylglycerol acylhydrolase, are members of the hydrolase family and operate on carboxylic ester bonds [38]. They belong to the class of serine hydrolases and don't need a cofactor[39]. Using natural lipases, triglycerides hydrolyse into diglycerides, monoglycerides, fatty acids, and glycerol (Fig. 1a). In addition to lipases, esterases can hydrolyse the carboxylic esters' bonds [40][41]

Fig:1 (a) Hydrolysis of triglyceride converts into glycerol and fatty acid. (b) Representation of a molecule of lipase with its features.

Between an insoluble phase of the substrate and an aqueous phase, where the enzymes continue to liquefy naturally, lipases catalyse the hydrolysis of ester bonds at the interface (Fig. 1b). Nevertheless, despite having a lid, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida antarctica* B, and *Burkholderia glumae* did not exhibit interfacial activation [42][43]. Lipases carry out the conversion reactions for esterification, transesterification, interesterification, acidolysis, alcoholysis, and aminolysis [44]. Carboxylesterase is a simple enzyme that catalyses the hydrolysis and synthesis of long-chain acylglycerols; the existence of a lid and interfacial activation are not appropriate criteria for classifying a real lipase [45].

2.2 Properties and characteristics of lipases

Lipases are reportedly monomeric proteins with molecular weights between 19 and 60 kDa. The physical characteristics of lipases are dependent on the fatty acid's degree of unsaturation, chain length, and location within the glycerol backbone [46]. These characteristics also have an impact on the triglyceride's sensory and nutritional qualities. Because they are active in organic solvents, a variety of lipases catalyse a variety of beneficial processes, including esterification [47]. In the absence of water, lipases can reverse the processes that result in esterification and interesterification under specific experimental conditions [48][49]. Lipases were separated into two groups based on their region-specificity and exposed to an acyl glycerol substrate. In the first group of lipases, solely fatty acids are released from all three glycerol sites without exhibiting regiospecificity [50][51]. Because of these characteristics, these enzymes can be employed to extract alcohols and esters that are optically pure. Utilising organic medium at low water activity presents a remarkable opportunity compared to variations of the solvent [52]. Therefore, altering the solvents' characteristics may change an enzyme's specificity. An enzyme's catalytic capabilities can be significantly impacted by any solvent because to its soft structures and fragile [53][54].

2.3 Kinetic model of lipolysis

Lipolysis occurs at the substrate/water contact, making the Michaelis-Menten model inapplicable. Only biocatalysis, where the enzyme and substrate are soluble, works well in a homogenous phase [55][56]. Simple models consisting of two successive equilibrium states have been developed at an interface to describe the kinetics of lipolysis [57]. A single substrate molecule binds to the adsorbed enzyme (E^*) in the first equilibrium phase, causing the enzyme to alterably adsorb to the interface ($E \leftrightarrow E^*$). This results in the formation of the (E^*S) complex in the second equilibrium phase [58]. The ensuing catalytic steps occur after the formation of the (E^*S) complex, which concludes with the release of the products and renovation of the enzyme in the (E^*) form [59][60]. In this model, the restored lipase remnant adsorbed to the interface and only becomes unconstrained following several catalytic cycles (**Fig. 2**). Lipase activity is a benefit of interfacial conformation: the interface is a good place to limit lipolysis, and the enzyme can be denatured as well as triggered or neutralised. The lipase inhibitor interacts directly with the enzyme and prevents lipase activity. However, a few chemicals can delay the lipolytic reaction by adhering to the substrate molecules or the interphase [61][62].

Fig:2 Lipase catalyzed different reactions

Lipase inhibitors are grouped into two categories:

(a) synthetic lipase inhibitors, such as fat analogues, phosphonates, and boronic acids, and (b) Natural substances include β -lactones and a number of botanical foodstuffs, including peptides, specific nutritional fibres, plant extracts, and metabolites, primarily polyphenols and saponins. Since lipases are necessary enzymes for the absorption of lipids, lipase inhibition regulates the absorption of fat or obesity. Lipase activity can be inhibited by natural chemicals called β -lactones, such as orlistat [63]. The hydrolysis of more than 80% of total dietary lipids is carried out by pancreatic lipase. Orlistat is the approved medication for the treatment of obesity in a number of nations [64].

3 Lipases inhibitors from microbial sources

Numerous metabolic compounds derived from microbes exhibit strong inhibitory effects on pancreatic lipase (PL). Numerous bacterial, fungal, and other marine species examined for new compounds with PL inhibitory activity as part of their ongoing hunt for a viable anti-obesity medication [65][66].

3.1 Sources for microbial lipases

Because they are more readily available, more stable, and less expensive to produce than lipases obtained from plants and animals, microbial lipases are widely distributed in nature and have substantial commercial potential. **Table 1.** Microbial lipases, both naturally occurring and recombinant, are extensively used in a variety of bioengineering applications [67]. The Dead Sea, Antarctica, alkaline lakes, hot springs, volcanic vents, and contaminated soils are just a few of the extreme environments to which the wide variety of microbial resources found in nature exhibit remarkable adaptability. This creates remarkable opportunities for the production of lipases with distinctive properties [68]. These enzymes are now more accessible due to significant developments in carboxyl esters and enantioselective hydrolysis. The ability to produce active enzymes and proteins is particularly boosted in marine microflora. Lipases are mostly extracellularly released by bacteria and fungi. *Candida antarctica* lipase B (CALB) is the most widely used enzyme and the subject of many patents in a variety of biocatalytic applications. The commercially available *C. rugosa* lipase (CRL), which is a mixture of several isoforms, is another significant lipase that is generated from yeast. This enzyme is used in the food business and is categorized as "Generally Recognized As Safe" (GRAS) [69]. *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, and *Streptomyces* are the bacterial genera that have been reconnoitered to produce lipases and phospholipases the most, followed by *Burkholderia*, *Chromobacterium*, *Achromobacter*, *Alcaligenes*, and *Arthrobacter* [70]. As indicated in Table 1, certain microbes that produce lipases disclose novel sources and uses for industrial enzymes.

Table 1 Microbial source of Lipase and their industrial application (Bacterial species)

Microbial source	Application	References
<i>Achromobacter sp. HEGN 014</i> , <i>Virgibacillus pantothenticus</i> <i>HEGN114</i>	Treatment of oily wastewater	[71]
<i>Pseudomonas mendocina</i>	Dishwashing/ laundry Removal of fast strain	[72]
<i>Acinetobacter radioresistens</i> ; <i>Bacillus sp. FHS</i>	Used in detergent industry	[73]

<i>Staphylococcus pasteurii</i>	Used in oil degradation	[74]
<i>P.fluorescens</i>	Enantioselective transesterification of a racemate (R,S)-4-methyl-1-heptyn-4-en-3-ol, a component of the insecticide S-2852	[75]
<i>Staphylococcus warneri</i> and <i>S. xylosum</i>	The production of flavour esters	[76]
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Used in leather processing	[77]
<i>Brevundimonas</i> sp. QPT-2	Involved in enantioselective degradation of AOPP herbicides	[78]
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	Commonly used detergents, enhance the removal of oily stains from various type of fabrics	[79]
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> HSS	Waste water treatment	[80]
<i>Marinobacter lipolyticus</i>	Organic Solvent- Tolerant Lipolytic enzyme	[81]
<i>Haloarcula</i> sp. G41	Organic solvent- tolerant lipase for biodiesel production	[82]
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Baking industry for bread making	[83]
<i>Geobacillus stearothermophilus</i>	Enhanced stability in methanol	[84]
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> HFE733	Biodegradation of oil and organics (determination as chemical oxygen demand (COD), biodegradation of food wastewater from restaurants	[85]
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Food processing and oil manufacture	[86]
<i>Natronococcus</i> sp.	Application in biocatalysis	[82]
<i>P.accaligenes</i> M-1	Alkaline lipases, able to removing fatty when used in a washing machine	[87]
<i>Pseudomonas plantarii</i>	Solvay Enzyme products, Application for is a nonionic and / or anionic detergent formulation	[88]
<i>Chromobacterium viscosum</i>	Detergent formulations containing alkaline lipase used in laundry detergent*Top*	[80]
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp.	Degrading 60-65% of the fatty material in the waste water management	[90]
<i>Bacillus thermocaterulatus</i>	Used in medical industry	[91]
<i>Penicillium roquefortii</i>	Cheese industry for cheese ripening	[92]
<i>Staphylococcus warneri</i> , <i>S.xylosum</i>	Production of flavour esters	[93]
<i>Pseudomonas ceacia</i>	Biodiesel fuel production	[94]
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Formation of (-)-15-deoxyspergualin 23) in drug industry as antitumor antibiotic and immunosuppressive agent.	[95]

3.2 Bacterial lipases

Bacterial lipases were initially discovered in 1901 in species like *B. fluorescens* and *B. prodigiosus*. As seen in **Fig. (3)**, *Serratia marcescens* and *P. aeruginosa* are now known to be the two bacteria that manufacture the most lipases. These enzymes fall into the lipoprotein and glycoprotein categories. Certain polysaccharides have an impact on the synthesis of lipases in a variety of bacterial species [96]

Fig: 3 The production of lipase enzyme from *P. aeruginosa* isolate using olive oil as a substrate in the phenol red agar (a) control medium showed the red color before growth, (b) showed growth of the microorganism at the center of the medium and change in the color of the pH-indicator (phenol red) into the yellow color due to lipase production

4 Isolation and identification of lipolytic bacteria from oil contaminated soil

Lipolytic bacteria were isolated from the soil sample using the plate count method. Nine millilitres of 0.85% sterile saline water were mixed with one gramme of soil samples. To generate 10–6 dilutions, 1 mL of an aliquot sample from each sample was transferred to 9 mL of 0.85% saline water. This process was known as serial dilution. Tween 80-supplemented nutrient agar and nutrient agar were plated with 0.1 mL of the diluted samples. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48–72 hours. To establish a pure culture, colonies with a zone of clearing were subcultured on nutrient agar and kept in a sterile nutrient slant for future research [97]. The microscopic and morphological features were used to identify the obtained pure culture. Gramme staining, catalase, citrate, oxidase, starch hydrolysis, methyl red Voges Proskauer, acid and gas generation from sugar fermentation, urease production, endospore formation, and motility tests were used to biochemically identify the organisms.

4.1 Screening of the isolates for lipase activity

Following a 48-hour incubation period at 37 °C, pure bacterial isolates were streaked on Tween 80 agar plates to screen for lipase production. Direct lipolysis, which is mechanically emulsified in multiple growth media, was used to observe changes in the substrate's appearance as it appeared on the petri dishes[98].

4.2 Selection of best isolates for lipase production

To identify the best lipase-producing bacteria, the isolates that could produce lipase were subsequently screened using the agar well diffusion (Cup well method). For the Agar well diffusion test, utilise a sterile Phenol Red Agar Plate with crude oil as the substrate. To create a 4 mm diameter well, these sterile agar plates were aseptically pierced using a sterile cork borer. After growing for 24 hours in 10 mL of sterile nutrient broth, the isolates were put into individual

wells using 50 μ L micropipettes and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C. The produced yellow zones surrounding the wells were measured in millimetres (mm), and the information was utilised to produce more enzyme[99].

4.3 Lipase production

Lipase was produced using the isolate with the larger zone on the phenol red agar plate. The following medium productions were prepared in accordance with this: crude oil (2 mL), Tween 80 (3 drops), $\text{NH}_4 \text{H}_2 \text{PO}_4$ (0.1 g), Peptone (0.2 g), $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.04 g), and NaCl (0.25 g). Submerged microbial cultures were incubated at 37 °C in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with 100 mL of liquid media on a rotary shaker set to 120 rpm. After 96 hours of incubation, the culture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 20 minutes at 4 °C, and the cell free culture supernatant was used to extract the extracellular enzyme sources[100][101][102].

5. Application of lipases

Because they are versatile and easy to produce in large quantities, microbial lipases have a wide range of industrial applications. Lipases are third among all enzyme groups in terms of total sales volume, after proteases and carbohydrases. The billion-dollar commercial use of lipases depends heavily on their specificity, ideal pH, temperature, and resistance to organic solvents, among other factors. Lipases are essential to a number of industries, including dairy, organic chemicals, pharmaceuticals, leather, food and fats, environmental management, agrochemicals, detergent, ole-chemicals, tea, cosmetics, and other bioremediation procedures[103].

Table 2: Application of lipases industry

Industry	Action	Product or application	References
Fats and oils	Transesterification; hydrolysis	Cocoa butter, margarine, fatty acids, glycerol, mon-, and diglycerides	[104]
Dairy foods	Hydrolysis of milk fat, cheese ripening, modification of butter fat	Development of flavoring agents in milk, cheese and butter	[105]
Bakery foods	Flavor improvement	Shelf-life prolongation	[106]
Beverages	Improved aroma	Beverages	[107]
Food dressings	Quality improvement	Spices and seasonings	[108]
Pharmaceuticals and Medical equipment	Transesterification, hydrolysis	Treatment of tumors, chiral drug resolution, antioxidants, digestive aids and Blood sensor	[109]
Pulp and paper	Hydrolysis	Paper with improved quality	[110]
Washing	Hydrolysis	Removal of fats	[111]
Biodiesel	Transesterification, hydrolysis, synthesis	Biodiesel production	[112]
Leather	Hydrolysis	Leather products	[113]

Cosmetics	Synthesis	Emulsifiers, moisturizers	[114]
Environmental protection	Transesterification, hydrolysis	Environmental detection and repair	[115]

Detergents

To increase the effectiveness of detergent formulations, lipases are combined with amylases and proteases. When water is added, lipases that have adhered to the fabric's surface form a stable fabric-lipases complex that catalyses the dissolution of chemical bonds [116]. These days, enzymes are the main ingredients in detergent formulas. Lipases, in particular, are crucial for removing stubborn fatty stains from fabric, such as butter, oil, etc., that are difficult to get rid of with regular washing. Because microbial lipases are essential for removing fatty residues from laundry, dishwashers, and blocked stains, the detergent business has grown to be one of the largest markets for them over the past 20 years. In addition to enhancing detergent efficacy, the use of these enzymes offers ecological acceptance and results in effluent that is less caustic and has a lower COD [117]. The following criteria are taken into consideration while choosing lipases for detergent formulation: (i) the ability to withstand rather harsh washing conditions (pH 9.0-11.0, 30-60 C); and (ii) the capacity to withstand harmful enzymes (proteases) and surfactants (linear alkyl benzene sulfonates), which are both major ingredients in many detergent formulations [118]. Novo Nordisk (Denmark) created Lipolase, the first recombinant lipase, for commercial use in 1994. *Thermomyces lanuginosus*-related genes were cloned, and a recombinant lipase called Lumafast was made available for purchase [119].

Food Industry

The main components of food are fats and oils. The position of the fatty acids in the glycerol molecule's backbone, the length of the fatty acid chain, and the degree of unsaturation all have a major impact on the triglyceride's physical and nutritional characteristics. By shifting the location of fatty acid chains inside triglycerides and replacing one or more of the existing fatty acids with new ones, lipases can modify the characteristics of lipids. A somewhat inexpensive and unappealing lipid can be transformed into a superior value fat in this manner [120]. When it comes to degumming vegetable oils, lipases are essential. Phospholipid contaminants in crude oils must be eliminated by this procedure in order to prevent problems during processing and storage. For instance, rapeseed and soybean oils can be efficiently degummed using lipases made by genetically modified *Aspergillus oryzae*, which remove over 90% of the phospholipids in 5 hours at 50°C [121]. Bacterial lipase (LIP A) combined with genetically modified baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) has demonstrated increased lipase productivity, making it a useful technical addition in breadmaking [122].

Diagnostic tools

lipases can indeed be used for diagnosing diseases. These enzymes, produced by various bacteria including *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Corynebacterium acnes*, can indicate infections or other conditions when their levels rise. Lipases blood tests are commonly used to diagnose pancreatic disorders such as acute pancreatitis. Elevated levels can signal inflammation or injury to the pancreas [123]. and *Staphylococcus aureus* [124]. Skin rashes in acne patients and the use of lipase

tests for diagnosing pancreatic conditions. Acne can indeed cause various types of skin lesions, including rashes. These rashes can be due to inflammation, bacterial infection, or irritation from acne treatments. Lipase is an enzyme produced primarily by the pancreas. A lipase blood test measures the amount of this enzyme in your blood [125]. Fungal lipases are versatile enzymes that can play a significant role in regulating triglycerides and cholesterol levels. These enzymes catalyze the hydrolysis of triglycerides into glycerol and fatty acids. Fungal lipases are produced by various fungi, including species like *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Rhizopus*. They are used in several industrial applications, including food processing, pharmaceuticals and biofuels.[126]

5 Ecological significance of microbial lipases

Oil-contaminated soils serve as enriched niches for lipase-producing microorganisms due to the abundance of hydrophobic substrates such as hydrocarbons and triglycerides. Microbes isolated from these environments, including species from genera such as *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, and *Rhodococcus*, often exhibit enhanced lipolytic activity, making them ecologically significant in natural attenuation and bioremediation processes. These lipases facilitate the breakdown of complex lipids and petroleum-based compounds into simpler, less toxic molecules, contributing to the detoxification and restoration of polluted soils. Moreover, by metabolizing oil-derived lipids, these microbes support microbial succession and biodiversity, fostering a more balanced and functional soil ecosystem. Their activity plays a central role in the carbon cycle under stress conditions, and some strains also produce biosurfactants that further enhance pollutant degradation. Thus, microbial lipases from oil-contaminated soils not only highlight adaptive microbial resilience but also represent valuable agents for ecological restoration and sustainable environmental management.

6 Future Perspective

The exploration of microbial lipases from oil-contaminated soils presents promising avenues for environmental biotechnology and sustainable remediation strategies. Future research should focus on the metagenomic and proteomic profiling of lipase-producing communities to uncover novel enzymes with superior stability, substrate specificity, and catalytic efficiency under extreme environmental conditions. Advancements in synthetic biology and genetic engineering could enable the development of engineered microbial strains or enzyme cocktails tailored for large-scale bioremediation of hydrocarbon-polluted sites. Additionally, integrating lipase-producing microbes with biosurfactant-producing consortia could significantly enhance the bioavailability and degradation rate of hydrophobic pollutants. Field-scale trials, alongside the development of cost-effective bioreactors and delivery systems, will be essential for translating laboratory findings into real-world applications. Furthermore, evaluating the long-term ecological impact and sustainability of such interventions will be crucial for their integration into environmental policies and restoration programs. The continued investigation into microbial lipases not only holds potential for ecological cleanup but also for applications in energy recovery, waste management, and green chemistry.

REFERENCES

1. Saranya P, Kumari HS, Rao BP and Sekaran G. Lipase production from a novel thermo-tolerant and extreme acidophile *Bacillus pumilus* using palm oil as the substrate and treatment of palm oil-containing wastewater. *Envir. Sci. Poll. Res.* (2014) 21: 39073919.CES
2. G. Kouker and K. Jaeger, "Specific and sensitive plate assay for bacterial lipases" *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 53, pp. 211-213, 1987.
3. B. Padmapriya, T. Rajeswari, E. Noushida, D. Sethupalan, and C. Venil, "Production of lipase enzyme from *Lactobacillus* spp. and its application in the degradation of meat," *World Applied Sciences Journal*, vol. 12, no. 10, pp. 1798-1802, 2011.
4. S. Hwang, K. Lee, J. Park, B. Min, S. Haam, and I. Ahn, et al. "Stability analysis of *Bacillus stearothermophilus* L1 lipase immobilized on surface-modified silica gels," *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 17, pp. 85-89, 2004.
5. F. Hasan, A. Sanh, and A. Hameed, "Industrial applications of microbial lipases," *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, vol. 39, pp. 235–251, 2005.
6. T. Hoshino, T. Sasaki, Y. Watanabe, T. Nagasawa, and T. Yamane, "Purification and some characteristics of extracellular lipase from *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. Lini," *Bioscience Biotechnology and Biochemistry*. vol. 56, pp. 660-664, 1992.
7. L. C. Ochoa, C. R. Gomez, G. V. Alfaro, and R. Ros, "Screening, purification and characterization of the thermoalkalophilic lipase produced by *Bacillus thermoleovorans* CCR11," *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, vol. 37, pp. 648–654, 2005.
8. S. A. Ericks and C. R. Rita, "Transesterification activity of a novel lipase from *Acinetobacter venetianus* RAG-1," *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek*, vol. 94, pp. 621–625, 2008.
9. Mobarak-Qamsari E, Kasra-Kermanshahi R and Moosavi-nejad Z 2011. Isolation and identification of a novel lipase-producing bacterium *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* KM110. *Iranian J. Microbiol.* 3(2): 92-98.
10. Awad G, Mostafa H, Danial EN, Abdelwahed NA and Awad HM 2015. Enhanced production of thermostable lipase from *Bacillus cereus* ASSCRC-P1 in waste frying oil-based medium using statistical experimental design. *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.* 5: 7–15.
11. Sztajer H, Maliszewska I, Wiczorek J. Production of exogenous lipase by bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 1988; 10:492–7.
12. Dutra, J. C. V., Terzi, S. C., Bevilacqua, J. V., Damaso, M. C. T., Couri, S., Langone, M. A. P. Lipase production in solid state fermentation monitoring biomass growth of *Aspergillus niger* using digital image processing. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology.* 2008; 147:63–75.
13. Griebeler, N., Polloni, A.E., Remonato, D., Arbter, F., Vardanega, R., Cechet, J.L. et al. Isolation and screening of lipase producing fungi with hydrolytic activity. *Food and Bioprocess Technology.* 2011; 4:578-586.
14. Hasan, F., A.A. Shah and A. Hameed. Industrial applications of microbial lipases. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 2006; 39: 235-251.
15. Abada, E. A. E. Production and characterization of a mesophilic lipase isolated from *Bacillus stearothermophilus* AB-1. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences.* 2008; 11: 1100–1106.
16. Ertuğrul S, Dönmez G, Takaç S. Isolation of lipase producing *Bacillus* sp. from olive mill wastewater and improving its enzyme activity. *J Hazard Mater* 2007; 149(3):720–4.
17. Kiran GS, Shanmughapriya S, Jayalakshmi J, Selvin J, Gandhimathi R, Sivaramakrishnan S, Arunkumar M, Thangavelu T, Natarajaseenivasan K. Optimization of extracellular

- psychrophilic alkaline lipase produced by marine *Pseudomonas* sp. (MSI057). *Bioprocess Biosyst. Eng.* 2008; 31: 483-492.
18. Wang S-L, Lin Y-T, Liang T-W, Chio S-H, Ming L-J, Wu P-C. Purification and characterization of extracellular lipases from *Pseudomonas monteilii* TKU009 by the use of soybeans as the substrate. *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 2009; 36: 6573.
 19. Kim K, Kwon D, Yoon S, Kim W, Kim K. Purification, refolding, and characterization of recombinant *Pseudomonas fluorescens* lipase. *Protein Expr. Purif.* 2005;39:124-129.
 20. Singh S, Banerjee U. Purification and characterization of trans-3-(4-ethoxyphenyl) glycidic acid methyl ester hydrolyzing lipase from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Process. Biochem.* 2007; 42: 1063-1068.
 21. Stoyanova Vasilena, Stanka Georgieva, Ivan Iliev, Mariana Marhova, Sonya Trifonova. Lipolytic activity of genus *Pseudomonas*. *J. BioSci. Biotech.* 2012; 163-168.
 22. Sierra G. A simple method for the detection of lipolytic activity of microorganisms and some observations on the influence of the contact between cells and fatty substrates. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 1957;23:15–22.
 23. Cardenas J, Alvarez E, de Castro-Alvarez M-S, SanchezMontero J-M, Valmaseda M, Elson SW, Sinisterra J-V. Screening and catalytic activity in organic synthesis of novel fungal and yeast lipases. *J Mol Catal B: Enzym.* 2001;14:111–23
 24. Yeoh HH, Wong FM, Lin G. Screening for fungal lipases using chromogenic lipid substrates. *Mycologia.* 1986;78: 298–300.
 25. Kouker G, Jaeger KE. Specific and sensitive plate assay for bacterial lipases. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 1987; 53:211–3.
 26. Gupta, R., Gupta, N., & Rathi, P. Bacterial lipases: An overview of production, purification and biochemical properties. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology.* 2004;64:763–781.
 27. Sharma, R., Chisti, Y. & Banerjee, U. C. Production, purification, characterization and applications of lipases. *Biotechnology Advances.* 2001;19:627–662.
 28. Menoncin.S, N.M. Domingues, D.M.G. Freire, G. Toniazzo, R.L. Cansian and J.V. Oliveira et al., Study of the extraction, concentration and partial characterization of lipases obtained from *Penicillium verrucosum* using solid-state fermentation of soybean bran. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 2010;3:537- 544.
 29. Bora L, Kalita MC. Production of thermostable alkaline lipase on vegetable oils from a thermophilic *Bacillus* sp. DH4, characterization and its potential applications as detergent additive. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol Int Res Proc Environ Clean Technol.* 2008;83(5):688–93.
 30. Bano K, Kuddus M, Zaheer MR, Zia Q, Khan MF, Gupta A, Aliev G. Microbial enzymatic degradation of biodegradable plastics. *Curr Pharma Biotechnol.* 2017;18(5):429–40.
 31. Özgen FF, Vardar-Yel N, Roth OS, Shahbaz LS, Vardar-Schara G. Surface residues serine 69 and arginine 194 of metagenome-derived lipase influence catalytic activity. *Biochem Eng J.* 2020;154:107442.
 32. Huang Y, Ren J, Qu X. Nanozymes: classification, catalytic mechanisms, activity regulation, and applications. *Chem Rev.* 2019;119(6):4357–412.

33. Challa S, Dutta T, Neelapu NRR. Fungal white biotechnology applications for food security: opportunities and challenges. In: Recent advancement in white biotechnology through fungi. Cham: Springer; 2019, p. 119–48.
34. Homaei AA, Sariri R, Vianello F, Stevanato R. Enzyme immobilization: an update. *J Chem Biol.* 2013;6(4):185–205.
35. Blamey JM, Fischer F, Meyer HP, Sarmiento F, Zinn M. Enzymatic biocatalysis in chemical transformations: a promising and emerging field in green chemistry practice. In: *Biotech Microb Enzym.* Academic Press; 2017, p. 347–403.
36. Prasad S, Roy I. Converting enzymes into tools of industrial importance. *Recent Patent Biotech.* 2018;12(1):33–56.
37. Casas-Godoy L, Duquesne S, Bordes F, Sandoval G, Marty A. Lipases: an overview. In: Sandoval G, editor. *Lipases and phospholipases. Methods in molecular biology*, vol. 861. Totowa: Humana Press; 2012.
38. Fetzner S, Steiner RA. Cofactor-independent oxidases and oxygenases. *Appl Microb Biotech.* 2010;86(3):791–804.
39. Beisson F, Tiss A, Rivière C, Verger R. Methods for lipase detection and assay: a critical review. *Eur J Lipid Sci Technol.* 2000;102(2):133–53.
40. Pascoal A, Estevinho LM, Martins IM, Choupina AB. Novel sources and functions of microbial lipases and their role in the infection mechanisms. *Physiol Mol Plant Pathol.* 2018;104:119–26.
41. Almeida JM, Martini VP, Iulek J, Alnoch RC, Moure VR, Müller-Santos M, Krieger N. Biochemical characterization and application of a new lipase and its cognate foldase obtained from a metagenomic library derived from fat-contaminated soil. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2019;137:442–54.
42. Stergiou PY, Foukis A, Filippou M, Koukouritaki M, Parapouli M, Theodorou LG, Papamichael EM. Advances in lipase-catalyzed esterification reactions. *Biotechnol Adv.* 2013;31(8):1846–59.
43. Damaso MCT, Salum TFC, Terzi SD, Couri S. Assay methods for lipase activity. In: Vermelho AB, Couri S, editors. *Methods to determine enzymatic activity.* Bentham: Rio de Janeiro; 2013. p. 161–94.
44. Jiao Y, Tang J, Wang Y, Koral TL. Radio-frequency applications for food processing and safety. *Ann Rev Food Sci Technol.* 2018;9:105–27.
45. Lei C, Guo B, Cheng Z, Goda K. Optical time-stretch imaging: principles and applications. *Appl Phys Rev.* 2016;3(1):011102.
46. Carpen A, Bonomi F, Iametti S, Marengo M. Effects of starch addition on the activity and specificity of food-grade lipases. *Biotechnol Appl Biochem.* 2019;66(4):607–16.
47. Veríssimo LAA, Mól PCG, Soares WCL, Minim VPR, Hespanhol MC, Minim LA. Development of a bioreactor based on lipase entrapped in a monolithic cryogel for esterification and interesterification reactions. *Revista Mexicana de Ing Química.* 2018;17(1):177–87.
48. Rmili F, Achouri N, Smichi N, Krayem N, Bayouhd A, Gargouri Y, Fendri A. Purification and biochemical characterization of an organic solventtolerant and detergent-stable lipase from *Staphylococcus capitis*. *Biotechnol Prog.* 2019;35(4):e2833.

49. Ekin AP, Dinçer B, Baltaş N, Adıgüzel A. Partial purification and characterization of lipase from *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* AH22. *J Enzym Inhibit Med Chem*. 2016;31(2):325–31.
50. Gaschler MM, Stockwell BR. Lipid peroxidation in cell death. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2017;482(3):419–25.
51. Dinanta Utama Q, Sitanggang AB, Adawiyah DR, Hariyadi P. Lipase-catalyzed interesterification for the synthesis of medium-long-medium (MLM) structured lipids—a review. *Food Technol Biotechnol*. 2019;57(3):305–18.
52. Yan Y, Li X, Wang G, Gui X, Li G, Su F, Liu T. Biotechnological preparation of biodiesel and its high-valued derivatives. *Rev Appl Energy*. 2014;113:1614–31.
53. Robinson PK. *Enzymes: principles and biotechnological applications*. *Essay Biochem*. 2015;59:1–41.
54. Eş I, Vieira JDG, Amaral AC. Principles, techniques, and applications of biocatalyst immobilization for industrial application. *Appl Microb Biotechnol*. 2015;99(5):2065–82.
55. Sarkar A, Zhang S, Holmes M, Ettelaie R. Colloidal aspects of digestion of Pickering emulsions: experiments and theoretical models of lipid digestion kinetics. *Adv Coll Interf Sci*. 2019;263:195–211.
56. Mat DJ, Le Feunteun S, Michon C, Souchon I. In vitro digestion of foods using pH-stat and the INFOGEST protocol: impact of matrix structure on digestion kinetics of macronutrients, proteins and lipids. *Food Res Int*. 2016;88:226–33.
57. Hitaishi VP, Clement R, Bourassin N, Baaden M, De Poulpique A, Sacquin-Mora S, Lojou E. Controlling redox enzyme orientation at planar electrodes. *Catalyst*. 2018;8(5):192.
58. Khodayari A, Zomorodi AR, Liao JC, Maranas CD. A kinetic model of *Escherichia coli* core metabolism satisfying multiple sets of mutant flux data. *Metabol Eng*. 2014;25:50–62.
59. Bansode SR, Rathod VK. An investigation of lipase catalysed sonochemical synthesis: a review. *Ultrasonics Sonochem*. 2017;38:503–29.
60. Amini Z, Ilham Z, Ong HC, Mazaheri H, Chen WH. State of the art and prospective of lipase-catalyzed transesterification reaction for biodiesel production. *Energy Convers Manag*. 2017;141:339–53.
61. Birari RB, Bhutani KK. Pancreatic lipase inhibitors from natural sources: unexplored potential. *Drug Discov Today*. 2007;12(19–20):879–89.
62. Xiao S, Yu R, Ai N, Fan X. Rapid screening natural-origin lipase inhibitors from hypolipidemic decoctions by ultrafiltration combined with liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry. *J Pharma Biomed Anal*. 2015;104:67–74.
63. de la Garza AL, Milagro FI, Boque N, Campion J, Martinez JA. Natural inhibitors of pancreatic lipase as new players in obesity treatment. *Planta Med*. 2011;77(8):773–85.
64. Drent ML, Van der Veen EA. Lipase inhibition: a novel concept in the treatment of obesity. *Int J Obesity Relat Metab Disord*. 1993;17(4):241–4.
65. Lunagariya NA, Patel NK, Jagtap SC, Bhutani KK. Inhibitors of pancreatic lipase: state of the art and clinical perspectives. *EXCLI J*. 2014;13:897.
66. Sánchez A, Vázquez A. Bioactive peptides: a review. *Food Qual Saf*. 2017;1(1):29–46.
67. Treichel H, de Oliveira D, Mazutti M, Oliveira JV. A review on microbial lipases production. *Food Bioprocess Technol*. 2009;3(2):182–96.

68. Chandra P, Enespa, Singh R, et al. Microbial lipases and their industrial applications: a comprehensive review. *Microb Cell Fact.* 2020;19:169.
69. Majumder D, Dey A, Ray S, Bhattacharya D, Nag M, Lahiri D. Use of genomics & proteomics in studying lipase producing microorganisms & its application. *Food Chemistry: Mol Sci.* 2024;9:100218.
70. Geoffrey K, Achur RN. Optimization of novel halophilic lipase production by *Fusarium solani* strain NFCCL 4084 using palm oil mill effluent. *J Genet Eng Biotechnol.* 2018;16(2):327–34.
71. Prieto SF, Smets J, Gil BE, Celades JF, Carda VJ, inventors; Procter, Gamble Co, assignee. Fluid detergent compositions comprising a di-amido gellant, and processes for making. United States patent US 8,168,579; 2012.
72. Hasan F, Shah A, Hameed A. Purification and characterization of a mesophilic lipase from *Bacillus subtilis* FH5 stable at high temperature and pH. *Acta Biologica Hungarica.* 2007;58(1):115–32.
73. Kiamarsi Z, Soleimani M, Nezami A, Kafi M. Biodegradation of n-alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons using novel indigenous bacteria isolated from contaminated soils. *Int J Environ Sci Technol.* 2019;16(11):6805–16.
74. Aleu J, Bustillo AJ, Hernandez-Galan R, Collado IG. Biocatalysis applied to the synthesis of agrochemicals. *Curr Organ Chem.* 2006;10(16):2037–54.
75. Ghori MI, Iqbal MJ, Hameed A. Characterization of a novel lipase from *Bacillus* sp. isolated from tannery wastes. *Brazil J Microb.* 2011;42(1):22–9.
76. Rozalen M, Huertas FJ, Brady PV. Experimental study of the effect of pH and temperature on the kinetics of montmorillonite dissolution. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta.* 2009;73(13):3752–66.
77. Nakamura T, Nagasawa T, Yu F, Watanabe I, Yamada H. Characterization of a novel enantioselective halohydrin hydrogen-halide-lyase. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 1994;60(4):1297–301.
78. Zarinviarsagh M, Ebrahimipour G, Sadeghi H. Lipase and biosurfactant from *Ochrobactrum* intermedium strain MZV101 isolated by washing powder for detergent application. *Lipid Health Dis.* 2017;16(1):177.
79. Chandra P, Singh DP. Removal of Cr(VI) by a halotolerant bacterium *Halomonas* sp. CSB 5 isolated from sāmbar salt lake Rajasthan (India). *Cell Mol Biol.* 2014;60(5):64–72.
80. Kim SJ, Park S, Kim HK. Characterization of organic solvent-tolerant lipolytic enzyme from *Marinobacter lipolyticus* isolated from the Antarctic Ocean. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol.* 2019;187(3):1046–60.
81. Li X, Yu HY. Characterization of an organic solvent-tolerant lipase from *Haloarcula* sp. G41 and its application for biodiesel production. *Folia Microbiol.* 2014;59(6):455–63.
82. Mnif I, Besbes S, Ellouze R, Ellouze-Chaabouni S, Ghribi D. Improvement of bread quality and bread shelf-life by *Bacillus subtilis* biosurfactant addition. *Food Sci Biotech.* 2012;21(4):1105–12.
83. Dror A, Shemesh E, Dayan N, Fishman A. Protein engineering by random mutagenesis and structure-guided consensus of *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* lipase T6 for enhanced stability in methanol. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 2014;80(4):1515–27.

84. Nitschke M, Costa SG, Haddad R, Gonçalves LAG, Eberlin MN, Contiero J Oil wastes as unconventional substrates for rhamnolipid biosurfactant production by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* LBI. *Biotechnol Prog.* 2005;21(5):1562–6.
85. Gerritse G, Hommes RW, Quax WJ. Development of a lipase fermentation process that uses a recombinant *Pseudomonas alcaligenes* strain. *Appl Env Microbiol.* 1998;64(7):2644–51.
86. Cardenas F, De Castro MS, Sanchez-Montero JM, Sinisterra JV, Valmaseda M, Elson SW, Alvarez E. Novel microbial lipases: catalytic activity in reactions in organic media. *Enzy Microbial Technol.* 2001;28(2–3):145–54.
87. Hasan F, Shah AA, Javed S, Hameed A. Enzymes used in detergents: lipases. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2010;9 (31):4836–44.
88. Wakelin NG, Forster CF. An investigation into microbial removal of fats, oils and greases. *Biores Technol.* 1997;59(1):37–43.
89. Yukselen O, Timucin E, Sezerman U. Predicting the impact of mutations on the specific activity of *Bacillus thermocatenulatus* lipase using a combined approach of docking and molecular dynamics. *J Mol Recogn.* 2016;29(10):466–75.
90. Talon R, Montel MC, Berdague JL. Production of flavor esters by lipases of *Staphylococcus warneri* and *Staphylococcus xylosus*. *Enzy Microb Technol.* 1996;19(8):620–2.
91. Toelstede S, Hofmann T. Kokumi-active glutamyl peptides in cheeses and their biogeneration by *Penicillium roquefortii*. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2009;57(9):3738–48.
92. Montel MC, Masson F, Talon R. Bacterial role in flavour development. *Meat Sci.* 1998;49:S111–23.
93. Fukuda H, Kondo A, Noda H. Biodiesel fuel production by transesterification of oils. *J Biosci Bioeng.* 2001;92(5):405–16.
94. Pérez MM, Gonçalves EC, Vici AC, Salgado JC, de Moraes MD. Fungal lipases: versatile tools for white biotechnology. In: *Recent advancement in white biotechnology through fungi.* Cham: Springer; 2019, p. 361–404.
95. Yeo SH, Nihira T, Yamada Y. Screening and identification of a novel lipase from *Burkholderia* sp. YY62 which hydrolyzes t-butyl esters effectively. *J Gen Appl Microbiol.* 1998;44(2):147–52.
96. LUZ BDDS, SARROUH B, BICAS, J. L., LOFRANO RCZ. Lipase production by microorganisms isolated from the Serra De Ouro Branco State Park. *An Acad Bras Cienc.* 2021;93(1):e20190672.
97. E. Mobarak-Qamsari, R. Kasra-Kermanshahi, Z. Moosavi-nejad Isolation and identification of a novel, lipase-producing bacterium, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* KM110. *Iran J. Microbiol.*, 3 (2) (2011), pp. 92-98.
98. N.A. Hassan, M.Z. Nawahwi, N. Yahya, N.A. Othman Identification and optimization of lipase producing bacteria from palm oil contaminated waste *J. Fundamental Appl. Sci.*, 10 (2S) (2018), pp. 300-310.
99. B. Mandepudi, D. Mandepudi, V.C. Ghanta Optimization of media parameters for the enhanced production and activity of lipase by bacteria lipase isolates *Int. J. Biol. Sci. Technol.*, 4 (4) (2012), p. 23.
100. S. Gaherwal, A. Lal, P. Chourasia, W. Nageshwar Studies on lipase producing bacterial strain isolated from different soil *Acad. J. Plant Sci.*, 7 (2015), pp. 1-5.

101. M. Patel, J. Mistry, S. Desai, S. Patel, S. Desai Isolation and characterization of lipase producing bacteria from vegetable oil spillage site *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 5 (8) (2016), pp. 214-232.
102. A.S. Ugbede, O.P. Abioye, S.A. Aransiola, O.A. Oyewole, N.R. Maddela, R. Prasa Production, optimization and partial purification of bacterial and fungal proteases for animal skin Dehairing: A sustainable development in leather production *Bioresour. Technol. Reports.*, 2023 (2023), Article 101632.
103. Verma N, Thakur S, Bhati A. Microbial lipases: Industrial applications and properties (A Review) . *International Research Journal of Biological Sciences.* 2012; 1: 88-92.
104. Konkrit, M., and Kim, W. (2016). Activities of amylase, proteinase, and lipase enzymes from *Lactococcus chungangensis* and its application in dairy products. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99, 4999–5007.
105. Esteban-Torres, M., Mancheño, J. M., De Las Rivas, B., and Muñoz, R. (2015). Characterization of a halotolerant lipase from the lactic acid bacteria *Lactobacillus plantarum* useful in food fermentations. *LWT Food Sci. Technol.* 60, 246–252.
106. Lamsal, B. P., and Faubion, J. M. (2009). Effect of an enzyme preparation on wheat flour and dough color, mixing, and test baking. *LWT Food Sci. Technol.* 42, 1461–1467.
107. Chandra, P., Enespa, Singh, R., and Arora, P. K. (2020). Microbial lipases and their industrial applications: a comprehensive review. *Microb. Cell Fact* 19:169.
108. Gricajeva, A., Kazlauskas, S., Kalėdienė, L., and Bendikienė, V. (2018). Analysis of *Aspergillus* sp. lipase immobilization for the application in organic synthesis. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 108, 1165–1175.
109. Dai, D., and Xia, L. (2005). Enhanced production of *Penicillium expansum* PED-03 lipase through control of culture conditions and application of the crude enzyme in kinetic resolution of racemic Allethrolone. *Biotechnol. Prog.* 21, 1165–1168.
110. Demuner, B. J., Junior, N. P., and Antunes, A. (2011). Technology prospecting on enzymes for the pulp and paper industry. *J. Technol. Manag. Innov.* 6, 148–158.
111. Kumar, A., Dhar, K., Kanwar, S. S., and Arora, P. K. (2016). Lipase catalysis in organic solvents: advantages and applications. *Biol. Proced Online* 18:2.
112. Khosla, K., Rathour, R., Maurya, R., Maheshwari, N., Gnansounou, E., Larroche, C., et al. (2017). Biodiesel production from lipid of carbon dioxide sequestering bacterium and lipase of psychrotolerant *Pseudomonas* sp. ISTPL3 immobilized on biochar. *Bioresour. Technol.* 245, 743–750.
113. Kavitha, M., Shanthi, C., and Chandrababu, N. K. (2018). Cold active lipase from *Pseudomonas* sp. VITCLP4 as degreasing agent in leather processing. *Indian J. Chem. Technol.* 25, 482–488.
114. Gupta, S., Gupta, C., Garg, A. P., and Prakash, D. (2015). A biotechnological approach to microbial based perfumes and flavours. *J. Microbiol. Exp.* 2, 11–18.
115. Lauprasert, P., Chansirirattana, J., and Paengjan, J. (2017). Effect of selected bacteria as bioremediation on the degradation of fats oils and greases in wastewater from cafeteria grease traps. *Eur. J. Sustain. Dev.t* 6, 181–186.
116. Hasan F, Shah AA, Hameed A. Industrial applications of miceobial lipases. *Enzyme microb Technol*, 2006; 39: 235- 251.

117. Nerurkar M, Joshi M, Paritis S, Adivarekar R . Application of lipases from marine bacteria *Bacillus sonorensis* as an additive in detergent formulation. *Journal of surfactants and detergents*. 2013; 13:,435-43.
118. Sharma R, Yusaf C, and Banerjee U.C. Production, purification, characterization and application of lipases. *Biotechnol Adv.*, vol.19 , pp.627-662,2001.
119. Jeon J H, Kim J T , Kim Y J , Kim H K, Lee H S, Kang S G, Kim J J and Lee J H. Cloning and characterization of a new cold active lipases from a deepsea sediment metagenome. *Appl Microbial Biotechnol.*, Vol. 81, pp 865- 874, 2009.
120. Undurraga D, Markovits A, and Erazo S . Cocoa butter equivalent through enzymic interesterification of palm oil mid fraction. *Process Biochem.*, vol.36, pp.933-939, 2001.
121. Sharma R, Chisti & Banerjee U C. Purification, characterization and application of lipases, *Biotechnol. Adv*, 19 , pp 627-662, 2001.
122. Yang J G, Wang Y H, Yang B, Mainda G, Guo Y. Degumming of vegetables oil by a new microbial lipases. *Food Technology and Biotechnology*, 44, 101,2006.
123. Higaki S , Kitagawa M, Kagoura M. Morohashi, and Yamagishi T. Correlation between propionibacterium acnes biotypes , lipases activity and rash degree in acne patients. *J Dermatol* , vol 27, pp 519-522, 2000
124. J. W. F. A. Simons, H. Adams, R. C. Cox, N. Dekker, F. Gotz, A. J. Slotboom, and H. M. Verheij, "The lipase from *Staphylococcus aureus*: Expression in *Escherichia coli*, large-scale purification and comparison of substrate specificity to *Staphylococcus hyicus* lipase." *Eur J Biochem.*, vol. 242, pp. 760-769, 1996.
125. R. Pezzilli, G. Talamini, and L. Gullo, "Behaviour of serum pancreatic enzymes in chronic pancreatitis." *Dig Liver Dis.*, vol. 32, pp. 233-237, 2000. *Liver Dis.*, vol. 32, pp. 233-237, 2000.
126. E. Schuster, N. Dunn-Coleman, J. Frisvad, and P. Van Dijck, "On the safety of *Aspergillus niger*-A review." *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.*, vol. 59, pp. 426-435, 2002.